

Middle East University
Faculty of Education

THE IMPACT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL
PRINCIPALS' EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON
TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY AND JOB
SATISFACTION IN LEBANESE PRIVATE SCHOOLS

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Zahia F. Dagher

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The Undersigned Faculty Committee Approves the

Thesis of

Zahia Dagher

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and Job Satisfaction in Lebanese Private Schools

Advisor

Reader

Dean

Date

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Zahia Dagher

ABSTRACT

This quantitative study sought to inspect secondary school teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction levels, to scrutinize the relationship among secondary school principals' emotional intelligence, teachers' self-efficacy and teachers' job satisfaction, and to investigate the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction levels. The sample comprised 9 school principals and 82 teachers of 9 private Lebanese Catholic and Evangelical schools. An emotional intelligence score was obtained for each principal by administering the Mayer-Salovey-Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test (MSCEIT). Teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction levels were measured by the "Teacher's Sense of Self-Efficacy Scale" and the "Job Descriptive Index." Principals yielded MSCEIT scores ranging from 77 to 91. The mean MSCEIT score is 100 with a standard deviation of 15. Teachers' self-efficacy results were relatively high with an average of 4.1 on a Likert Type five point rating scale. Also, their job satisfaction levels were relatively high with a score of 81% on the positive items and only 10% on the negative ones of the "Job in General" scale of the Job Descriptive Index. A comparison among principals' MSCEIT scores and teachers' produced self-efficacy and job satisfaction averages and percentages was made. Furthermore, associations among the 3 variables were analyzed by conducting a correlational research utilizing factor analysis and partial least square modeling (PLS) to conclude that a direct positive correlation exists between principals' emotional intelligence and teachers' self-efficacy $r=0.58$ and principals' emotional intelligence and job satisfaction levels $r= 0.31$. Also, a direct positive correlation was evident between teachers' self-efficacy and job satisfaction levels $r=0.45$.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

MHS	Multi-health Systems
MEIS	Multi-branch Emotional Intelligence Scale
MSCEIT	Mayer, Salovey, Caruso Emotional Intelligence Test
RAND CORPORATION	Research and Development Corporation
EQ-I	Emotional Quotient Inventory
ECI-2.0	Emotional Competence Inventory
TES	Teacher Efficacy Scale
TSES	Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale
PTE	Personal Teacher Efficacy
GTE	General Teacher Efficacy
ERIC	Educational Resources Information Center
JDI	Job Descriptive Index
E EI	Experiential Emotional Intelligence
SEI	Strategic Emotional Intelligence
SEM	Structural Equation Modeling
EFA	Exploratory Factor Analysis
CFA	Confirmatory Factor Analysis
PLS	Partial Least Square

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DEDICATION

To the one who cradled my entity
With the purest genres
Of unconditional love
And was sent to me
From above
To the one who incessantly
Endeavored to be a father
And a mother at the same time
And endlessly melted
And died so I can shine
In my life, everything was so murky
There was no light
Until you came
And gave me sight
You walked me step by step
Through the cruel valleys of life
Together hand in hand
We transcended strife
And when the going
Got rough you said daughter
Daughter you are
Enough tough
You never failed
To be near
And was always ready
To obliterate my fear
The loving things
You did for me
I can never repay
In any demeanor or way
I do not want to imagine
How life would have
Tasted without your presence
Undoubtedly twisted tormented
And void of any essence
I just want you to know
That you live inside me
Wherever I go
And our special moments I
Will always cherish
Until the day I perish

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